

Table 1: Ethical principles identified in the primary studies

Ethical Principle	Reference	New	Summary
1. Accuracy	[1]	-	AI systems should maintain maintain a high level of accuracy in order to ensure optimal functionality.
2. Autonomy	[1, 2]	Yes	Promoted through transparency and predictable AI, by not ‘reducing options for and knowledge of citizens’, by actively increasing people’s knowledge about AI, giving notice and consent or, conversely, by actively refraining from collecting and spreading data in absence of informed consent [3]
3. Social well-being	[4]	-	AI systems should benefit individuals and society [5].
4. Beneficence	[1]	Yes	Defined as the augmentation of human senses, the promotion of human well-being and flourishing, peace and happiness, the creation of socio-economic opportunities, and economic prosperity [3]
5. Trust	[2]	Yes	Include calls for trustworthy AI research and technology, trustworthy AI developers and organisations, trustworthy ‘design principles’, or underline the importance of customers’ trust [3]
6. Human dignity	[1]	Yes	Artificial intelligence can be harnessed to cultivate human nature and its potentialities, generating opportunities, avoiding opportunity costs, and mitigating risks [6]
7. Diversity	[2, 4, 7]	-	AI systems should be designed to promote diversity in order to avoid any discriminatory practices and to achieve a fair outcome [7]
8. Effectiveness	[1]	-	AI systems should perform their designated functions in an optimal manner, utilising the available resources in a way that ensures the desired outcomes are achieved
9. Fairness	[1, 2, 4, 7]	Yes	AI systems should be inclusive and accessible, and should not involve or result in unfair discrimination against individuals or groups [5]
10. Explainability	[1, 7–9]	-	Defined by what the AI system is doing and why, and may include the system’s processes and input data [5]
11. Interpretability	[1, 9]	-	An interpretable model should provide users with a description of the meaning of a given input, such as a data point or model output, in the context of the wider system [5]
12. Justice	[1]	-	Mainly expressed in terms of fairness, and of prevention, monitoring or mitigation of unwanted bias and discrimination [3]
13. Legality	[7]	-	AI systems should comply with all relevant legislation at every stage of the process, including data collection, design, output and implementation [7]
14. Non-discrimination	[4]	-	AI systems should be designed in such a way that they are incapable of engaging in any discriminatory practices
15. Non-maleficence	[1, 2]	Yes	Encompass general calls for safety and security or state that AI should never cause foreseeable or unintentional harm [3]
16. Predictability	[1]	-	Having a system that does what we expect it to do [10]

17. Privacy	[2, 4]	Yes	Often presented in relation to data protection and data security [3]
18. Prosperity	[1]	-	AI systems should disseminate their benefits equitably among all members of society [6]
19. Accountability	[1, 2, 4, 7]	Yes	Acting with ‘integrity’ and clarifying the attribution of responsibility and legal liability, if possible upfront, in contracts or, alternatively, by centering on remedy [3]
20. Robustness	[4, 7]	-	AI systems should have procedures to ensure fail-safe operation in unexpected situation, and operate in a predictable and explainable manner [4]
21. Security	[2, 4, 7]	Yes	It is essential that AI systems operate reliably throughout their lifecycle in the context of their intended purpose, and that they are protected against any potential security breaches [5]
22. Data governance	[1, 4, 7]	Yes	AI systems should ensure data quality and restrict data access to individuals with the appropriate credentials [4]
23. Solidarity	[1]	Yes	Defined in relation to AI and the labour market, with a focus on ensuring that the benefits of AI are shared fairly to maintain social cohesion and protect those who are vulnerable [3]
24. Human oversight	[4]	Yes	AI systems should support human decision-making rather than making decisions for humans [4]
25. Sustainability	[1]	Yes	Calls for development and deployment of AI to consider protecting the environment, improving the planet’s ecosystem and biodiversity, contributing to fairer and more equal societies and promoting peace [3]
26. Transparency	[1, 2, 4, 8]	Yes	Ensure people know when they are being significantly impacted by an AI system, and can find out when and how an AI system is engaging with them. Closely related to explainability and interpretability [3, 5]

References

- [1] A. A. Khan, S. Badshah, P. Liang, B. Khan, M. Waseem, M. Niazi, and M. A. Akbar, “Ethics of ai: A systematic literature review of principles and challenges,” 2021.
- [2] N. K. Corrêa, C. Galvão, J. W. Santos, C. Del Pino, E. P. Pinto, C. Barbosa, D. Massmann, R. Mambrini, L. Galvão, E. Terem, and N. de Oliveira, “Worldwide ai ethics: A review of 200 guidelines and recommendations for ai governance,” *Patterns*, vol. 4, no. 10, p. 100857, 2023.
- [3] A. Jobin, M. Ienca, and E. Vayena, “The global landscape of ai ethics guidelines,” *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 1, no. 9, p. 389–399, Sep. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>
- [4] V. Vakkuri, K.-K. Kemell, J. Tolvanen, M. Jantunen, E. Halme, and P. Abrahamsson, “How do software companies deal with artificial intelligence ethics? a gap analysis,” in *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software*

- Engineering*, ser. EASE '22. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530030>: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 100–109.
- [5] C. Sanderson, D. Douglas, Q. Lu, E. Schleiger, J. Whittle, J. Lacey, G. Newnham, S. Hajkovicz, C. Robinson, and D. Hansen, “Ai ethics principles in practice: Perspectives of designers and developers,” *IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 171–187, Jun. 2023.
- [6] L. Floridi, J. Cowls, M. Beltrametti, R. Chatila, P. Chazerand, V. Dignum, C. Luetge, R. Madelin, U. Pagallo, F. Rossi, B. Schafer, P. Valcke, and E. Vayena, “Ai4people—an ethical framework for a good ai society: Opportunities, risks, principles, and recommendations,” *Minds and Machines*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 689–707, Dec 2018.
- [7] C. Rees and B. Müller, “All that glitters is not gold: trustworthy and ethical ai principles,” *AI and Ethics*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1241–1254, Nov 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00232-x>
- [8] N. Balasubramaniam, M. Kauppinen, A. Rannisto, K. Hiekkänen, and S. Kujala, “Transparency and explainability of ai systems: From ethical guidelines to requirements,” *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 159, p. 107197, 2023.
- [9] H. Vainio-Pekka, M. O.-O. Agbese, M. Jantunen, V. Vakkuri, T. Mikkonen, R. Rousi, and P. Abrahamsson, “The role of explainable ai in the research field of ai ethics,” *ACM Trans. Interact. Intell. Syst.*, vol. 13, no. 4, dec 2023.
- [10] V. Vakkuri, K.-K. Kemell, J. Kultanen, and P. Abrahamsson, “The current state of industrial practice in artificial intelligence ethics,” *IEEE Software*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 50–57, 2020.